

Gasification of Water Hyacinth (*Eichornia Crassipes*).

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In continuation of our work already published (Sen, Pal, and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 673), it was considered of interest to investigate the technical gasification of this plant in view of its abundant growth in certain tropical non-saline waters. According to a report of the Special Officer appointed by the Government of Bengal, the plant spreads over an area of 4269 sq. miles in Bengal alone, choking many important waterways, and causing great agricultural loss. Pending any effective method of eradicating the pest rapidly, the question of utilisation naturally deserves consideration. Three methods of utilisation of this weed have been investigated in this laboratory, an account of which is recorded below :

(1) *Saccharification* by acid digestion and subsequent *fermentation* has already been described (*loc. cit.*). This aspect of the problem assumes more than ordinary interest in view of the publication of the Scholler Patent in June, 1929 (B. P. 273.317), which claims a practically quantitative conversion of cellulose into fermentable sugar by means of pressure percolation with dilute sulphuric acid.

(2) *Gasification of Water Hyacinth by Air and Steam*.—This process is essentially similar to that attempted elsewhere for the utilisation of peat. Water hyacinth is an aquatic plant characterised by a very high percentage of water content like that of peat, as much as 95% when fresh. The nitrogen content is also

almost similar to that of peat, being mostly over 2%. The ash content is much higher, reaching up to 22% at times of which 55 to 60% is practically pure potassium chloride. This renders recovery-distillation more economical. A pound of steam-oven dried sample has a calorific value of 6530 B. T. U., whilst the ordinary sun-dried sample containing approximately 16% moisture has a calorific value of 5580 B. T. U. The plant will, therefore, bear no profitable gasification with more than 80% water content as the whole of the fuel value of the plant would then be used up in evaporating and super-heating the water contained therein. Mere sun-drying reduces the moisture content to 16%. This is quite comparable to the working at Orentano in Italy where the peat is reported to have been brought to the producers with 30—35% water. With this water content there appears to be efficient working. Frank claims that peat containing up to 50% water can be treated in Mond producers to yield 70—80% of its nitrogen as ammonium sulphate (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1908, 32, 580). Caro and Frank (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1910, 23, 1844) go still further and consider even 60% water content as being workable. Haanel (*Canada Dept. of Mines, Mines Branch, Ottawa, Bulletin No. 154*) whose critical review in this direction is very important, opposes this figure, and maintains that "under the most ideal conditions—which do not and cannot obtain in actual practice—the quantity of heat generated by the burning of such peat is not sufficient to effect the various reactions and provide for losses and simultaneously give a power gas of the heating value claimed."

Our laboratory experiments were performed with sun-dried water hyacinth containing approximately 16% moisture, which is about the condition in which it is available after a fortnight's stacking in the sun. A silica tube was at first wrapped up with a few layers of asbestos paper, and then wound round with nichrome wire. The tube was enclosed in a wider sheet-iron casing, the annular space being packed with well-ignited magnesia. The outer casing was finally covered with a thick sheet of asbestos board in order to prevent quick radiation. Such a furnace lasted on an average 20 to 30 heatings up to 980°. The silica tube carried a thermocouple at one end reaching almost to the middle in order to ensure a fairly accurate average temperature prevailing at the time of the experiment. The introduction of air and steam was effected from the other end of the silica tube by means of an aspirator working on the

distillate end as shown in Fig. 1. The volume of water delivered by

FIG. 1.

G, gasometer; C, superheating coil; F, electric furnace;
W, sulphuric acid wash-bottle; A, aspirator bottle; P, pyrometer; T, tar-catcher.

the aspirator during the experiment was necessarily equivalent to the volume of gas collected whilst the gasometer, *G*, indicated the volume of air introduced in the particular experiment. The receiver, *T*, and the sulphuric acid washer, *W*, retained any ammoniacal vapours generated in course of the gasification. Their contents were afterwards distilled with alkali, the volatile base absorbed in standard acid and expressed as ammonia. The volume of gas obtained per ton of sun-dried water hyacinth works out at approximately 40,000 cft., having under working conditions a calorific value of 142 B.T.U. The ammonium sulphate was on an average 100 pounds to the ton of water hyacinth. The residue after gasification is a dull grey ash, quite loose if the temperature is not allowed to exceed 1000°. This mass on extraction with water and evaporation of the solution, yields 2 cwts of potassium chloride of 95% purity.

Below are given the results of a few of the numerous experiments on gasification:

Water hyacinth used (in grams)	100	100	100	100
Furnace temperature	720—730°	720—730°	800—810°	960—980°
Air saturation temperature	75°	80°	70°	75°
Air volume	3.9 cft.	3.75 cft.	3.25 cft.	3.3 cft.
Time of gasification	3 hrs. 13 mins.	1½ hrs.	3 hrs.	1½ hrs.
Ammonia	1.17	0.94	0.82	

Water hyacinth used (in grams)	100	100	100	100
Volume of gas collected (in litres)	130	134	138	135
Hydrogen (per cent.)	12	16.14	16.6	19.7
Methane (per cent.)	1.2	1.5	4.8	nil
Carbon monoxide (per cent.)	14.03	12.8	21.7	22.1
Carbon dioxide (per cent.)	5.0	6.5	4.1	3.4
Nitrogen (per cent.)	67.0	—	52.8	—

Calculating from the blast saturation temperature of 75—80° we find that 39g. of moisture are carried over for every 100 g. of water hyacinth, or 0.39 ton of steam per ton of air-dried water hyacinth. Carbon dioxide is evidently less, as some of it must have dissolved in the aspirator water at 31°.

(3) *Bacterial Decomposition of Water Hyacinth.*—The fairly large quantity of hemi-cellulose in the weed naturally suggested the possibility of utilising the weed by bacterial fermentation. Some preliminary experiments were already published (Sen, Pal, and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*), and since the appearance of a controversy between Fowler and Weston in a local trade journal (*Minutes of the Proceedings of the Institute of Civil Engineers*, Vol. 226, p. 32. *The Capital*, 1929, Vol. 83, pp. 482, 602) the question has been subjected to a more critical investigation. These results are given below:

The green water hyacinth as it is collected from canals or large tanks, contains 95% water, about 4% organic matter, and 1% mineral matter. This is first of all macerated by pounding in an iron vessel by a pestle to small shreds, and the whole carefully transferred to a large and tall winchester bottle (3 litres capacity usually) containing sewage of a definite volume. The water content of the plant taken was separately determined in an equivalent sample in order to allow for it in subsequent calculations. No special precaution for maintaining constant temperature was taken. The temperature between March and April was usually 32° in the laboratory. All experiments were checked against controls, and gas volumes were corrected accordingly. A typical result is given below:—

196 Grams of green water hyacinth containing 80 per cent. moisture gave with $\frac{3}{4}$ litre sewage the following volumes of gas.

	Gas collected.	Control.
First day (24 hrs.)	1875 c.c.	500 c.c.
Second day	3750	500
Third day	4320	500
Fourth day	3100	350
Fifth day	3100	300
Sixth day	2600	200
Seventh day	2100	159
Eighth day	1560	100
Ninth to twelfth day	3650	200
Thirteenth to fifteenth day	1100	120
	Total gas collected 27,155 c.c.	2,920 c.c.

Surplus gas due to the fermentation of water hyacinth (196 g.) = 24,235 c.c. collected over water at 31°. 196 G. of 80% moist water hyacinth correspond to 39.2 g. of dry matter of which 16.4 g. correspond to α -, β -, and γ -celluloses. Roughly speaking, therefore, for every gram of total cellulose together with its attendant lignin and other organic matters, 1475 c.c. of gas of the average composition, $\text{CO}_2 = 22.1\%$, $\text{O} = 1.2\%$, $\text{CH}_4 = 51.6\%$, $\text{H} = 25.4\%$ were collected. Towards the end on the tenth day the composition of the gas varied considerably, giving decidedly larger volumes of methane and little of hydrogen:

Methane	70%
Hydrogen	3.8
Carbon dioxide	25.2
Nitrogen and oxygen, by diff.	1.0

This would point to an independent methane—carbon dioxide fermentation as has been observed by some workers before.

Whilst the fermentability of smashed green hyacinth is great, that of the dry plant is distinctly sluggish. This, improves, however, on the dry plant being digested under heat and pressure with slightly acidulated water. The yield of gas is still far less, being about half of that obtained from the green material. So far, under best possible conditions of working, 26,500 cft. of gas per 20 tons of green water hyacinth (1 ton of dry material), having a calorific value of 602 B. T. U. have been obtained. On several occasions much smaller values, as low as half of this has been

recorded. In no case, however, the fermentation entirely stopped until after 3 weeks.

In order to ascertain whether the gas produced from lignocellulose fermentation is fundamentally different from that evolved in the bacterial decomposition of pure cellulose, 5 g. of the best Swedish filter paper were treated with $\frac{3}{8}$ litre of the same sewage with the following results:—

	Gas collected.	Control.		Gas collected.	Control.
First day (24 hours)	500 c.c.	250 c.c.	Seventh day	500 c.c.	75 c.c.
Second day	1000	250	Eighth to tenth day	650	50
Third day	1000	250	Eleventh to fifteenth day	600	75
Fourth day	850	150			
Fifth day	750	100			
Sixth day	500	75	Total	6350 c.c.	1275 c.c.

The total gas from 5 g. of filter paper, therefore, is 5075 c.c. or approximately 1000 c.c. per g. of cellulose. The average composition of this gas mixture is somewhat different, being poorer in hydrogen.

Methane	79.2 per cent.
Carbon dioxide	15.0
Hydrogen	2.7
Nitrogen	3.1

Whether this decided poverty of hydrogen in pure cellulose fermentation is due to the absence of other secondary groups which are so largely present in lignocelluloses need not be entered upon here.

Further work in this direction is already in progress.

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